

ACTIVITY AND PERSONALITY OF BUKHARA EMIRI SAYID OLIMKHAN

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Abstract: This article is devoted to the discussion of the uniqueness of the personality of the emir of Bukhara, Syed Alim Khan, his activities, and his place in history. The purpose of the article is to study the political views of Amir Syed Alim Khan, discuss his personal life and analyze his life path.

Key words: Bukhara, Amir Syed Alim Khan, Young Bukhara people, Turkestan, Kabul, Afghanistan, Qal'ai Fatuh, Amonullah Khan, English, Bolsheviks, Nicholas II.

INTRODUCTION

Syed Olimkhan is the last emir of the Bukhara Emirate from the Mangits. Studied at the Nikolaev (pages) corps in St. Petersburg (1893-96). In 1898, Karshi became the governor of the Karmana provinces as the crown prince. After the death of his father, on December 24, 1910, he ascended the throne of Bukhara. During his time, the dependence of the Bukhara Emirate on Russia became stronger. The progressive forces, as well as the Young Bukharans, were severely persecuted. During the First World War, Russian Emperor Nicholas II awarded him the military rank of lieutenant general and appointed him as his adjutant general (December 1915). Because he helped Russia with a large amount of money. On the eve of the First World War and in the years after the events of the war, the properties of Bukhara citizens were in Iran, East Turkestan (China), India and other Eastern countries, in a number of cities of the Russian Empire, and the emir's money was in the banks of Russia, England, Switzerland, France, and India. was. A number of studies have been published about the foreign real estates and funds of Bukhara emirs Abdulahad Khan (reign: 1885-1910), Syed Olim Khan (reign: 1910-1920). One of the grandsons of Amir Alim Khan, Syed Mansoor Alimi, expressed his opinion in his memorial book: "Amir Alim Khan's sons have appealed to London and Pakistan several times and asked for the return of their real money, but this money is still hanging in the air." brings [1, p. 32].

Many articles and works were written about the last ruler of the Bukhara Emirate, Syed Alim Khan (1881-Bukhara, 1944-Kabul, 1910-1920) and his historical fate in the last years of independence. It is worth noting that researches that shed light on the political image of Amir Olimkhan and his life path also serve to study important aspects directly related to the history of our country.

In the first quarter of the 20th century, the political processes in the Zarafshan oasis and in the entire Turkestan region, the issues related to Amir Olimkhan are also considered [2, p. 181].

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In his memoirs, Amir Alim Khan explains the reasons for moving to the territory of Afghanistan, his visit to the Afghan emir Amonullah Khan (1919-1929) in the city of Kabul, his leadership of the Mujahideen movement, and his appeals to international organizations and

major countries for help. brings related information. On March 4, 1921, Amir left the Chubek tributary of the Vakhsh River in the Kolob region of Tajikistan, followed by 200-250 thousand (50 thousand families) Uzbeks and Tajiks to neighboring Afghanistan. In the 1920s, 35,000 Turkmen families from the Kerki and Chorjoi Bekliks also occupied the emirate with 2 million Turkmens. they moved to the territory of the neighboring country with their cattle [3, 592-p.].

The reasons for Amir Olimkhan's emigration to the country of Afghanistan, that is, the factors in the choice of this region and the future life path of the emir, the political situation at that time, among the researchers Mir Ghulam Gubor, Sayyid Mansur Olimi, K.Abdullaev, Q. Rajabova's scientific research has been described to some extent.

The above-mentioned authors prove that Amir Alim Khan's emigration to Afghanistan was caused by his inability to withstand the attack of the Reds. In particular, K.Abdullaev, relying on foreign sources, said that the country chosen by the emir to live in exile - Afghanistan, was located on close borders with each other, that the long-distance border line was empty at that time, He enumerates one after the other reasons such as the existence of cooperative relations between the emirs of Bukhara, the religious factor. Research shows that Amir Alim Khan was welcomed as a guest in Kabul, the capital of Afghanistan. The Amir's first residence in Kabul was Husayn Kawt Park, soon he was moved to Hashim Khan Park, and then to Muradbek Castle. Fatuh Castle, located 11 km from Kabul, was the last residence of the emir. Amir lived on the allowance of 12,000 Afghani rupees (later 14,000 rupees) set by the Afghan government and the income from a jewelry store with a capital of 1 million gold soums [4, p. 284].

Particular attention is paid to the personality traits of Amir Olimkhan, his family life during his stay in Bukhara and his emigration. In this direction, the works of N. Naimov, A. Egamnazarov, M. Olimpur, M. Hasani, Rajabboy Ataturk, Q. Rajabov, S. Jalilov can be listed.

In the summer of 1923, by the decision of the government of the USSR, Amir Syed Olimkhan's mothers Toraoyim, Shamsiyaoyim, To'tioyim, daughters Khosiyatoy, Saodatoy, wives Muharramoyim, Musharrafoyim, Mubarakoyim, Khursandoyim, uncles Mir Muhammad Siddiq Muzaffarkhan son, Mir Nasir Muzaffarkhan son Mir Abdul Azim Khan Muzaffar Khan, sister Shokhai, birth mother Davlat Bakht and other close relatives were sent to Afghanistan at their own discretion. "At the beginning of the 90s of the 20th century, 2 wives, 12 sons and 10 daughters were alive. They lived in Ghaziantib, Turkey, as well as in the USA, Germany, Afghanistan, Pakistan, Saudi Arabia and Iran. They visited Bukhara in September 1993", - writes Q. Rajabov.

Amir married several times while in exile and had 37 children abroad, 16 sons and 21 daughters.

Syed Alim Khan had many descendants, according to some sources, they are about 500. In the last years of Amir's life, except for a few, almost all his descendants were with him. In late August 1920, Syed Alim Khan began to hastily evacuate himself, his family, and several relatives as the Red Army rapidly encircled and began bombarding and invading Bukhara. However, probably because of the sudden forced evacuation, his three young sons - 8-10 years old (according to other sources, 4-6 years old), Sultanmurad, Shahmurad and Rahimkhan remained in Bukhara. . After the capture of Bukhara, the Bolsheviks found them and initially tried to shoot them, along with some of the emir's remaining family members and close associates (similar to how Nicholas II was executed with his family and close associates), but gave up. kept them alive and sent all three to Moscow to raise them in an orphanage for

orphans of dead Bolsheviks and soldiers of the Red Army to carry out propaganda in their favor.

According to the authors, the emir had conversations and meetings with Afghan emirs Amonullah Khan (1919-1929), Bachai Saqo (1929, January-October), Nadirshah (1929-1933), Muhammad Zahirshah (1933-1973). Amir Olimkhan asked them for help in the fight against the Bolsheviks. However, the Afghan emirs ignored his requests. Amir's desire to continue the struggle against Soviet power will be unsuccessful. After Anvar Pasha (1881-1922) was defeated in military clashes in the summer of 1922 and died in Baljuvan, many of Anvar Pasha's "printers" fled to Afghanistan, to the emir [5, p. 460].

RESULTS

The research also provides information about the personal characteristics of Amir Olimkhan. Amir Olim Khan had positive qualities and held "bedilkhan" and "poetry evenings" in Qal'ai Fatuh in Kabul. He organized a competition between the Afghan football team from Kabul and the immigrant Uzbek team "Turon" and awarded prizes to those who showed exemplary performance in the competition. Amir set an example to other immigrant Uzbeks in wearing oriental national clothes and preserving our national traditions and values. Amir's son, Syed Umar Khan, born in Afghanistan, said: "Our father, a rogue, loved hunting. They went hunting with Amir Amonullah Khan and showed their marksmanship. In the photo, the Afghan emir is depicted in European clothes, and our father in Bukharan clothes," he recalls [239].

Amir Alim Khan hired teachers to teach his children, to teach them foreign languages such as English and Urdu. In Kabul, his children were taught by brothers Khoja Rahmatullah and Khoja Karomatullah from Mirabad, British India. Among the children of Amir Olimkhan, poets, journalists, doctors, and statesmen grew up.

CONCLUSION

Although Amir Olimkhan lost his political position, British and Soviet intelligence agencies were interested in him at the same time. An English spy named Agha Muhammad, nicknamed "Dorivor", lived with his mother in the garden of the emir and gave information to England about the emir and his family.

A person named Narzulla lived in Amir's Fatuh garden in Kabul and worked as a tea maker. He reported to the British who came to the emir every day, and took 600 kolders from them in a month.

Amir Alim Khan lived in Afghanistan with love and passion for the Motherland. We hope that in the future, more perfect and original research will be done on the issue of Amir Olimkhan's personality and his life as an emigrant.

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